

Introduction: An increasing number of lunar missions are planned for the coming decade, requiring the establishment of a robust communication and navigation architecture. Such an architecture relies on accurate time synchronisation between lunar missions and Earth-based systems. Currently, this time data primarily comes from Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS). However, GNSS time synchronisation cannot be reliably ensured around the Moon due to limited line-of-sight between the lunar orbits or the lunar surface and the Earth. Creating a lunar analogue to GNSS represents both a tremendous technical and political challenge. This work evaluates the feasibility of consensus-based, decentralised time synchronisation in lunar networks, which promises greater robustness and independence than centralised approaches. The analysis is based on the needs of the LunaNet concept proposed by NASA, ESA, and JAXA [1], a common framework enabling cooperation among institutions with lunar missions in a shared communication and navigation network.

Traditionally, time distribution and synchronisation are centralised, with a master node broadcasting its time value to all other nodes in a network. In distributed methods, a common time value is often determined by consensus. Nodes exchange their on-board software time data and iteratively correct their synchronisation error based on received data until all nodes agree on a common clock time. Such methods have the advantage of being less sensitive to the failure of a single mission or malicious activity like signal jamming or spoofing.

Lunar satellite networks pose specific challenges to decentralised time synchronisation. They will likely include heterogeneous missions comprising relay satellites, science orbiters, and surface assets like rovers or landers. Such networks will be small and sparsely connected, especially in the early phases of lunar exploration, and inherently dynamic and time-varying due to the orbital motions. The growth of lunar networks over time introduces the problem of joining new nodes with potentially different opinions of the current time value to an already established consensus without disrupting synchronisation. Additionally, communication with Earth and between satellites in highly eccentric orbits introduces large variations in the expected communication delays. Furthermore, cooperation among missions from different space agencies or companies entails heterogeneous communication capabilities and results in directed links due to differing communication ranges.

Simulations: The Decentralised Asynchronous Resilient Time Synchronisation (DARTS) framework [2] was evaluated for three simulations capturing challenges associated with lunar networks, with each simulation building in the level of realism it depicts. DARTS is designed to prevent outlier values from dominating the synchronisation process, whether from faulty or malicious nodes. This is achieved by having nodes gather data from neighbouring nodes' broadcasts before applying a filtering algorithm to remove the most extreme values from the dataset. The Matryoshka Orbital Networks framework [3] was used to generate contact plans of lunar networks with orbiting and surface-bound nodes.

A first simulation showed that a new node can join small, static networks without disrupting an already established consensus. This was done by allowing a new node to broadcast its clock time only after it is sufficiently close to its internally calculated consensus value, with the node recognising that it is an outlier within the system. This approach ensures that new nodes with extreme opinions do not broadcast misleading information that would corrupt the consensus.

In a second simulation, dynamic, small, and sparse lunar networks were simulated to determine the network characteristics (e.g. size, connectivity, contact duration) needed to allow for consensus to be reached. This is especially important for the early phases of LunaNet when sparse connectivity can be expected between very few missions. Monte-Carlo simulations were run for networks of different sizes combining orbiting nodes and a ground station. For each tested scenario, orbit parameters were generated from random distributions with bounds chosen based on current research on lunar navigation satellite systems [4–6]. The simulation showed that larger networks are more likely to agree than smaller networks. Additionally, individual nodes need to be connected to other nodes for sufficient durations to receive enough data from the rest of the network via two-hop links.

In a third simulation, a new node was introduced into small, sparse lunar networks, combining simulations one and two. The effect of different network sizes and ratios of surface to orbiting nodes was analysed, as well as the difference between a newly joining surface node and a joining orbiting node. As shown in Figure 1, the identity of the joining node affects convergence speed, and well-connected surface nodes converge faster than orbiting nodes with only intermittent contact to the network.

Figure 1: Time to convergence when introducing a new node to lunar networks sampled from (a) 40 fully connected surface nodes, (b) 40 surface nodes and 40 satellites, and (c) 40 satellites, with convergence defined for an absolute node time difference smaller than $50 \cdot 10^{-9}$

The simulations show that achieving a synchronisation time of 50 ns is feasible with DARTS for the considered challenges of small, sparse, and growing lunar networks with three or more nodes. For comparison, current GNSSs require timing performance better than 40 ns [7]. However, DARTS does not consider all challenges faced by lunar networks, for example disregarding communication delays. For future use, a better adapted algorithm is needed.

Lunar networks like LunaNet will start with few satellites but for suitable contact plans, decentralised time synchronisation can already be achieved early on. Increasing network size promises faster and more robust convergence. However, the future constellation design and specifically its contact plan may be crucial for the success of lunar consensus-based timekeeping.

Other effects on the time synchronisation process and its accuracy need to be considered: relativistic corrections due to the differing rates of time on the Earth and Moon, hardware limitations of on-board oscillators such as temperature effects and clock stability, and the maximum synchronisation level inherent for specific algorithms.

The use of decentralised time synchronisation in a lunar network may additionally serve as a testing ground for robust and autonomous time determination in deep-space systems like a solar system internet [8]. The challenges faced by a deep-space architecture are similar, if not more extreme than those of lunar networks.

Conclusion: A decentralised approach to time synchronisation for LunaNet and other lunar networks offers robustness and autonomy, as well as providing GNSS-equivalent levels of time synchronisation accuracy. The DARTS algorithm proves to be suitable for simplified lunar networks. The simulations further showed that for future use in LunaNet, a specifically designed algorithm is needed.

References: [1] LunaNet (2025) LunaNet Interoperability Specification Document: Version 5. [2] Bouis A. et al. (2025) *AIAA Aviation Forum and ASCEND*. [3] Gribben J. et al. (2023) *74th IAC*. [4] Bhamidipati S. et al. (2023) *NAVIGATION*, 70.4. [5] Grenier A et al. (2022) *NAVIGATION*, 69.2. [6] Cosby M. and Tai W. (2022) The Future Lunar Communications Architecture: Report of the Interagency Operations Advisory Group. [7] Zhu L. et al. (2022) *Sensors*, 22.7, 2486. [8] ESA (2025) *ESA Strategy 2024: In Depth*.